

1 *Type of the Paper (Review)*

2 **Recent Developments in Hemocompatible Surface Coatings**

3 **Erick Iles¹, María José Flores¹ Anthony Anrango and Raul Davalos Monteiro¹**

4 ¹ School of Biological Science and Engineering, Universidad Yachay Tech, San Miguel de Urququí, Urququí,
5 100119, Ecuador

6 **Abstract**

7 Hemocompatible coatings are critical for improving the performance and safety of
8 blood-contacting cardiovascular devices. This review provides a comprehensive over-
9 view of the current landscape of surface modifications, focusing on heparinized coat-
10 ings, diamond-like carbon (DLC) layers, zwitterionic hydrogels, and endothelial-mi-
11 metic nitric oxide (NO)-releasing surfaces. We analyze the mechanisms of action, design
12 strategies, immobilization approaches, advantages and limitations, and recommended
13 metrics for evaluating coating performance under physiological shear and flow condi-
14 tions. Clinical and preclinical evidence from stents, vascular prostheses, catheters, extra-
15 corporeal circuits, mechanical valves, and ventricular assist devices (VADs) is summa-
16 rized, highlighting the translational relevance of each technology. Hybrid coatings, com-
17 bining active anticoagulant function with passive antifouling or tribological enhance-
18 ments, emerge as the most promising strategy for long-term hemocompatibility. Key
19 gaps in the field include the lack of standardized evaluation protocols, limited long-term
20 clinical validation, and insufficient comparative studies across device types and coating
21 technologies. We propose a decision framework linking device type, flow regime, and
22 coating strategy, alongside an integrated hemocompatible index to facilitate quantitative
23 comparison and guide future development. This synthesis provides researchers and cli-
24 nicians with a practical reference for selecting and evaluating hemocompatible surfaces,
25 emphasizing the balance between mechanical durability, biological function, and clinical
26 applicability.

27 **Keywords:** Hemocompatibility; Surface modification; Blood–material interactions

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29 **1. Introduction**

30 Since the earliest attempts at vascular repair —dating back to vessel ligation prac-
31 tices recorded around 200 B.C. —the evolution of cardiovascular surgery has been
32 marked by a continual struggle to achieve functional and durable blood-contacting ma-
33 terials. The first artificial vascular prosthesis was introduced in 1894, followed by the
34 implantation of mechanical and biological heart valves in the 1950s and the advent of
35 transcatheter valve replacement in 2000. Despite these milestones, device performance
36 has remained limited by adverse blood–material interactions [45]. The realization that
37 material composition and surface properties critically determine thrombogenicity and
38 biocompatibility shifted research focus from purely mechanical functionality toward he-

39 mocompatible design. This transition laid the foundation for modern surface engineer-
40 ing strategies and biofunctional coatings aimed at mitigating clot formation and inflam-
41 mation in cardiovascular devices [46].

42 Currently, blood-contacting medical devices face significant limitations in their clini-
43 cal applicability due to insufficient understanding and optimization of hemocompatibil-
44 ity. Adverse interactions between blood and biomaterials, such as those used in vascular
45 grafts, stents, catheters, and extracorporeal circuits, can lead to activation and destruc-
46 tion of blood components, contributing to complications such as thrombosis, inflamma-
47 tion, and device failure. Hemocompatibility refers to the ability of a material to function
48 in direct contact with blood without inducing harmful biological responses, such as clot
49 formation, complement activation, or hemolysis [47].

50 The one common denominator among all blood-contacting devices is the inevitable
51 interaction between polymeric biomaterials and blood. This contact cannot be avoided,
52 as implantation inherently involves tissue injury and blood exposure. When blood en-
53 counters a foreign surface, a complex cascade of biological events is initiated —beginning
54 with the rapid adsorption of plasma proteins such as fibrinogen, albumin, and immuno-
55 globulins. These proteins often undergo conformational changes that expose binding
56 domains capable of activating platelets and leukocytes. Subsequent amplification of the
57 coagulation cascade and complement system promotes thrombus formation and inflam-
58 matory responses. While coagulation is essential for hemostasis and wound closure, it
59 becomes detrimental in cardiovascular contexts, where thrombosis can obstruct blood
60 flow and cause severe complications such as stroke or cardiac arrest. Because these inter-
61 actions are multifactorial, no single material property —chemical composition, surface
62 roughness, or energy — can independently ensure hemocompatibility. Therefore, surface
63 engineering must address multiple molecular and cellular pathways to maintain a deli-
64 cate balance between biocompatibility and hemostatic control [48,49].

65 Thrombus formation and hemolysis remain leading causes of failure in blood-con-
66 tacting medical devices such as vascular grafts, stents, and ventricular assist systems,
67 underscoring the ongoing clinical need for materials that maintain long-term hemocom-
68 patibility. To mitigate these complications, surface engineering strategies —particularly
69 the development of hemocompatible and low-friction coatings —have become a central
70 focus of biomaterials research [50]. Coatings such as heparin-functionalized layers, hy-
71 drogels, diamond-like carbon (DLC), and endothelial-mimetic surfaces have shown
72 promise in reducing thrombogenicity, minimizing protein adsorption, and enhancing
73 mechanical stability under physiological flow. Yet, no single coating approach has
74 proven universally effective across all device types or operating conditions. Further-
75 more, the clinical performance of these coatings is often limited by challenges related to
76 durability, delamination, and loss of bioactivity over time. Despite considerable pro-
77 gress, our understanding of how coating composition, fabrication methods, and surface
78 physicochemistry modulate biological responses remains incomplete [51]. This high-
79 lights the need for an integrated evaluation of coating technologies that bridges mecha-
80 nistic insights with clinical outcomes to guide the design of next-generation hemocom-
81 patible materials.

82 In this study, a bibliographic search was conducted to gather recent and high-qual-
83 ity literature related to vascular devices and hemocompatibility. The inclusion criteria
84 considered publications from the last five years, focusing on peer-reviewed journals
85 ranked in Quartile 1 (Q1) and Quartile 2 (Q2). The search strategy employed Boolean

86 operators and the following keywords: “Stents”, “CBAS”, “heparin”, “Catheters”,
87 “drug-eluting stents”, “intravascular catheters”, and “hemocompatibility”. Studies that
88 did not meet the publication date or journal quality criteria were excluded from the re-
89 view. This review systematically examines current hemocompatible and low-friction
90 coating technologies—including heparin-based, diamond-like carbon (DLC), zwitteri-
91 onic hydrogel, and endothelial-mimetic approaches—with an emphasis on their mecha-
92 nisms, fabrication strategies, performance metrics, and clinical translation. By comparing
93 recent preclinical and clinical evidence, we aim to highlight the strengths, limitations,
94 and unresolved gaps that must be addressed to develop next-generation blood-contact-
95 ing devices with sustained hemocompatibility and mechanical durability

96 **2. Classification of Biomedical Coatings and Mechanisms**

97 Surface modification strategies for blood-contacting materials can be broadly classi-
98 fied according to their dominant mechanism of hemocompatibility enhancement. These
99 include biochemical coatings that inhibit coagulation (e.g., heparin-based systems),
100 physical or tribological coatings that minimize friction and wear (e.g., diamond-like car-
101 bon), and antifouling or hydration-based coatings that resist nonspecific protein adsorp-
102 tion (e.g., zwitterionic hydrogels). In addition, bioactive and endothelial-mimetic coat-
103 ings aim to replicate physiological regulation through local release or catalytic genera-
104 tion of signaling molecules such as nitric oxide (NO). The following sections summarize
105 key developments, mechanisms, advantages, and evaluation metrics for each coating
106 family, highlighting current trends and performance trade-offs.

107 *2.1. Heparinized Coatings (Biochemical Anticoagulant Mechanisms)*

108 Heparin is one of the most widely used anticoagulant agents on hemocompatibility
109 surfaces due to its ability to inhibit thrombin and reduce platelet activation [1]. Recent
110 studies highlight self-healing heparin systems, which maintain anticoagulant activity
111 after washing or sterilization cycles [2]. Maitz et al. (2025) reported in their studies that
112 heparin-polyethylene glycol networks retain more than 85% of their anticoagulant activ-
113 ity after 30 days of immersion in plasma, reducing protein adsorption by 70% compared
114 to PTFE [3]. In neurovascular devices, Chen et al. (2024) demonstrated that a heparin-
115 polyacrylamide hydrogel reduced thrombus formation in simulated arterial flow by 60%
116 [4]. However, leaching and loss of anchorage remain critical limitations, especially under
117 high shear conditions ($> 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) [5].

118 *2.1.1. Mechanism and objective*

119 Heparin-based coatings act primarily through a main biochemical mechanism: im-
120 mobilised heparin enhances the activity of antithrombin III against thrombin and factor
121 Xa, thereby reducing fibrin generation and thrombus formation at the blood-material
122 interface. In properly designed coatings, this effect can be complemented by local reduc-
123 tion of protein adsorption and platelet activation [6].

124 *2.1.2 Immobilization strategies*

125 The two main approaches are covalent bonding (silanes, epoxides, amide bonds)
126 and layer-by-layer (LbL) assemblies that alternate polysal or polymers with heparin or
127 sulphate analogues. Covalent bonding maximises functional retention and minimises
128 leaching, while LbL allows control of density and functional porosity but may be more

129 susceptible to loss under flow. Recent studies have described heparin-mediated net-
130 works and self-repairing formulations that combine anticoagulant activity with the abil-
131 ity to recover from mechanical damage, demonstrating efficacy in in vitro and in vivo
132 study models [7].

133 *2.1.3. Advantages and limitations*

134 The main advantage of using heparin and its derivatives is their clinically known
135 direct anticoagulant activity; in addition, it is possible to combine heparin with additive
136 functions (antimicrobial, self-repair). Limitations include the potential leaching of poly-
137 saccharides, loss of activity due to chemical modifications or non-validated sterilisation
138 processes, and uncertainty about functional durability under high arterial shear. For this
139 reason, the evaluation should include post-sterilisation activity retention and testing un-
140 der shear conditions relevant to the application [8].

141 *2.1.4. Recommended metrics*

142 It is recommended to study functional density (IU/mm² or equivalent), percentage
143 of activity retention after X cycles/time, platelet activation tests (P-selectin, aggregation),
144 coagulation markers (TAT), and quantitative leaching tests under flow conditions [9].

145 *2.2. Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC) and Carbon Derivative Coatings (Physical–Tribological Mecha-* 146 *nisms)*

147 *2.2.1. Mechanism and objective*

148 Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings are amorphous carbon materials character-
149 ized by variable sp³/sp² ratios that determine their mechanical and tribological proper-
150 ties. Their combination of high hardness, low surface roughness, and tunable surface en-
151 ergy results in a reduced coefficient of friction and excellent wear resistance—critical fea-
152 tures for components exposed to dynamic blood flow such as valves, pumps, and mov-
153 ing interfaces. In blood-contacting environments, these physical properties aim to mini-
154 mize shear-induced platelet activation and surface-induced thrombus formation while
155 enhancing mechanical durability [10].

156 *2.2.2. Immobilization strategies*

157 The hemocompatibility of DLC coatings depends strongly on surface chemistry
158 and defect control, as microcracks or delamination can expose reactive sublayers that
159 promote fibrinogen adsorption and platelet adhesion. To address these challenges, recent
160 strategies have focused on surface modification and multilayer design, including doping
161 with elements such as fluorine, nitrogen, or silicon to tailor surface energy and minimize
162 protein adsorption; the incorporation of gradient interlayers to enhance adhesion to me-
163 tallic or polymeric substrates and prevent delamination under cyclic fatigue; and the de-
164 velopment of hybrid architectures that combine DLC with ultrathin functional topcoats—
165 such as zwitterionic or PEG-based layers—to provide additional antifouling properties
166 without compromising the coating's inherent wear resistance [11,12].

167 *2.2.3. Advantages and Limitations*

168 The main advantages of DLC coatings include their outstanding mechanical
169 strength, low friction coefficient, and resistance to corrosion and wear. They also tend to

170 promote a favorable albumin/fibrinogen adsorption ratio, which supports hemocompati-
171 bility. However, limitations arise from their sensitivity to surface defects, potential brit-
172 tleness under cyclic stress, and variable biological performance depending on the sp^3/sp^2
173 ratio and surface chemistry. In some cases, excessive fibrinogen adsorption may negate
174 their tribological benefits, especially in small-diameter vascular grafts [11].

175 2.2.4. Recommended Metrics

176 The evaluation of DLC coatings should integrate mechanical, chemical, and
177 biological parameters to ensure reliable performance under physiological conditions.
178 Key assessments include measuring film thickness (nm– μ m) and the sp^3/sp^2 ratio using
179 Raman spectroscopy to characterize structural composition; determining adhesion
180 strength through scratch testing and evaluating the coefficient of friction using pin-on-
181 disc or reciprocating tests in physiological media; and conducting protein adsorption
182 assays—typically quantifying fibrinogen and albumin in μ g/cm²—to assess surface
183 affinity. Additionally, platelet activation and adhesion should be quantified to evaluate
184 thrombogenic potential, alongside hemolysis and cytocompatibility tests performed
185 under dynamic flow conditions to simulate in vivo environments [13].

186 2.3. Zwitterionic hydrogels (pMPC, pSB, pCB) and reinforced formulations

187 2.3.1. Mechanism and objective

188 Zwitterionic polymers, such as phosphorylcholine (pMPC), sulfobetaine (pSB), and
189 carboxybetaine (pCB), exhibit remarkable antifouling properties due to their ability to
190 form a tightly bound hydration layer, or “hydration shell,” that resists nonspecific pro-
191 tein adsorption and cell adhesion. When configured as hydrogels, these materials pro-
192 vide not only biochemical inertness but also mechanical cushioning, effectively reducing
193 friction at blood–material interfaces. This dual antifouling and low-friction behavior
194 makes them highly attractive for applications requiring both hemocompatibility and
195 mechanical compliance [14].

196 2.3.2. Immobilization strategies

197 A major challenge with zwitterionic hydrogels has been their limited mechanical
198 robustness and weak adhesion to substrates, which compromise durability under shear
199 and cyclic loading. To overcome these issues, recent approaches have focused on devel-
200 oping reinforced microgel composites, dynamic or reversible cross-linking networks,
201 and in situ–curable “zwitterionic paints” that can form stable, uniform layers on various
202 substrates. These strategies significantly improve interfacial adhesion, fatigue resistance,
203 and long-term retention of antifouling properties under physiological flow [15].

204 2.3.3. Advantages and Limitations

205 The principal advantage of zwitterionic hydrogels lies in their exceptional re-
206 sistance to protein fouling and platelet adhesion, often outperforming traditional hydro-
207 philic polymers such as PEG. Moreover, their inherent lubricity supports applications in
208 dynamic blood-contacting environments. However, limitations include potential swell-
209 ing or mechanical degradation over prolonged exposure, difficulties in large-scale fabri-
210 cation, and challenges in ensuring consistent adhesion on complex geometries [15].

211 2.3.4. Recommended Metrics

212 Evaluation of zwitterionic hydrogel coatings should include quantification of
213 plasma protein adsorption reduction (relative to control), platelet adhesion reduction
214 percentage, coefficient of friction (CoF) under plasma lubrication, and functional
215 retention after defined flow exposure times and shear rates. Additional tests assessing
216 mechanical fatigue resistance and adhesion strength are recommended to validate long-
217 term performance [16].

218 *2.4. Endothelial-Mimetic and NO-Releasing Coatings*

219 *2.4.1. Mechanism and objective*

220 Endothelial-mimetic coatings aim to replicate the natural antithrombogenic and
221 anti-inflammatory properties of the vascular endothelium. Central to this approach is
222 the local release or catalytic generation of nitric oxide (NO), a key signaling molecule
223 that inhibits platelet activation, suppresses smooth muscle proliferation, and promotes
224 vascular homeostasis. By providing a biomimetic chemical environment, these coatings
225 seek to reduce thrombogenicity and facilitate re-endothelialization on blood-contact-
226 ing surfaces [17].

227 *2.4.2. Immobilization strategies*

228 Two primary strategies are employed: (i) physical incorporation of NO donors,
229 such as S-nitroso thiols, into porous polymeric or sol-gel matrices for controlled release;
230 and (ii) immobilization of catalytic agents (e.g., copper, organ selenium complexes) that
231 continuously generate NO from endogenous blood precursors like S-nitroso thiols. Each
232 method requires precise control over release kinetics, coating stability, and sterilization
233 compatibility to maintain long-term bioactivity [16].

234 *2.4.3. Advantages and Limitations*

235 The principal advantage of zwitterionic hydrogels lies in their exceptional re-
236 sistance to protein fouling and platelet adhesion, often outperforming traditional hydro-
237 philic polymers such as PEG. Moreover, their inherent lubricity supports applications in
238 dynamic blood-contacting environments. However, limitations include potential NO-
239 releasing coatings effectively suppress platelet adhesion and inflammatory activation
240 while supporting endothelial cell growth, offering superior biological integration com-
241 pared to passive coatings. However, challenges remain regarding donor depletion, cata-
242 lyst inactivation, and maintaining safe, sustained NO fluxes within physiological ranges.
243 Moreover, their mechanical and chemical stability under high-flow or cyclic stress con-
244 ditions still require optimization for long-term clinical use [16].

245 *2.4.4. Recommended Metrics*

246 Evaluation should include NO release rate ($\text{nmol}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), functional duration
247 (hours–days–weeks), platelet activation and aggregation assays (percentage reduction
248 relative to control), hemolysis and cytocompatibility testing, and re-endothelialization
249 assays using endothelial cell cultures on coated substrates [17].

250 *3.2. Comparative summary and design recommendations*

Trade-offs: Passive families such as DLC and zwitterionic materials excel in durability and friction reduction; active families such as heparin and NO provide direct anticoagulant action but often face temporary stability issues. On the other hand, hybrid coatings such as DLC + zwitterionic layer or covalent heparin + NO generator emerge as the best

Material / Coating Type	Key Composition or Functionalization	Main Hemocompatible Mechanism	References
Heparin-based coatings	Covalent or electrostatic immobilization of heparin or heparinoids on metallic or polymeric substrates.	Anticoagulant activity via antithrombin III activation; reduced platelet adhesion and protein adsorption.	[2], [7], [11]
Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC)	Amorphous carbon films doped with Si, N, or Ag to enhance surface energy and biostability.	Low surface energy minimizes fibrinogen adsorption; high wear resistance ensures long-term hemocompatibility.	[10]
Zwitterionic hydrogels	Poly(sulfobetaine) or carboxybetaine-based hydrogels, sometimes combined with PEG or silica hybrid networks.	Hydration shell formation prevents nonspecific protein adsorption and platelet activation.	[2], [3], [19]
Endothelium-mimetic coatings	NO-releasing or glycocalyx-like polymer coatings integrating zwitterionic or PEG-based copolymers.	Mimic endothelial functions: nitric oxide release, reduced inflammation, and improved cell compatibility.	[1], [20]

compromise options, provided that adhesion and functional retention are validated in tribo-hematic tests replicating clinical shear regimes [3], [11].

Mandatory experimental evaluation: To compare technologies and techniques, it is necessary to report CoF in physiological media (same protocol), quantitative protein adsorption (in plasma), platelet activation (markers), leaching tests, and functional retention after sterilization and mechanical fatigue. In addition, detailing shear rates is critical for clinical extrapolations [13], [18].

4. Clinical applications and translational evidence of hemocompatible coatings:

In this section we will analyze how hemocompatible and low-friction coatings have been applied in real devices or animal models, how effective they have been under blood flow conditions, and what are their known limitations.

4.1. Stents, implantable vascular devices and vascular prostheses

Coronary or arterial stents represent highly demanding cardiovascular devices in terms of blood-material interaction, given that their surfaces are directly exposed to high flows and recirculation zones where thrombi can form. In these environments, the hemocompatibility of the coating can determine the rate of in-stent thrombosis and the clinical success of the implant [21], [22]. Traditionally, some stents incorporate immobilized heparin, for example, using CARMEDA BioActive Surface (CBAS) technology, with the purpose of inhibiting local coagulation and reducing thrombus formation [23]–[26].

278 The CBAS surface is one of the most established in this field, with extensive pre-
279 clinical and clinical support. Its proponents emphasize that immobilized heparin re-
280 mains functional even after months or years in the bloodstream and that its anticoagu-
281 lant capacity, such as neutralizing thrombin or factor Xa, is preserved [27]. Furthermore,
282 this coating has been shown to tolerate balloon expansion, as occurs in stent deploy-
283 ment, while maintaining its antithrombotic activity [27]. However, despite these encour-
284 aging results, comparative studies with drug-eluting stents (DES) have shown heteroge-
285 neous findings: while some report benefits, others show no significant differences, sug-
286 gesting that the mere presence of heparin does not always translate into consistent clini-
287 cal improvement [28], [29].

288 A current review of stent coatings notes that, although heparin coating is effective
289 and safe in many cases, some randomized trials found no significant differences in
290 thrombosis or restenosis between heparin-coated and non-heparin-coated stents [30].
291 This suggests that in the presence of modern antiplatelet therapies or optimized stent
292 designs, the added advantage of heparin may be marginal. Faced with this situation,
293 several authors [20]–[22], [26], [30] suggest that the evolution should be directed towards
294 hybrid coatings that combine heparin with other functions such as anti-fouling proper-
295 ties, controlled drug release, or endothelial mimicry to overcome the limitations of a
296 monofunctional approach. In line with this trend, authors describe the use of biomolecu-
297 lar interfaces such as heparin with collagen using layer-by-layer techniques to improve
298 not only hemocompatibility but also the ability to support endothelialization without
299 inducing hyperplasia [20], [31].

300 Even so, the literature emphasizes that the effectiveness of coatings depends not
301 only on their composition but also on their mechanical and chemical stability. The cova-
302 lent bond of heparin can be compromised during stent expansion, loading and flexing
303 cycles, or prolonged exposure to high shear rates. Furthermore, heparin leaching re-
304 mains a critical issue: if it is not firmly immobilized, it can be released into the plasma,
305 losing localized activity and generating unwanted systemic effects. In this regard, sev-
306 eral authors highlight the need to optimize both the immobilization chemistry and the
307 coating's resistance to prolonged physiological conditions ([21], [22], [24]–[26], [32]).

308 Another interesting case is biomineralized heparin/TiO₂ coatings on polyurethane
309 for vascular applications. These inorganic-organic hybrid coatings combine the anticoag-
310 ulant bioactivity of heparin with the mechanical robustness and chemical stability of
311 TiO₂, which have demonstrated wear resistance, antimicrobial activity, and improved
312 adhesion [8]. These coatings show promise for applications in repetitive vascular grafts
313 and conduits, although they are still in the preclinical phase.

314 In the field of small-caliber vascular prostheses, where the surface-to-volume ratio
315 and high shear stress promote thrombosis and intimal hyperplasia, the most recent ad-
316 vances point to combined modifications to reduce protein adsorption and platelet activa-
317 tion without impairing medium-term endothelialization. Recent work highlights that
318 heparin modification and well-anchored zwitterionic layers can improve initial blood
319 flow, while the micro/nanoarchitectural design of the lumen favors mid-term endo-
320 thelialization. These sources also underscore the importance of reporting pulsatile shear
321 conditions, long exposure times, and comparable metrics [33].

322 *4.2. Catheters, extracorporeal tubes and blood circuits*

Beyond stents, recent advances have shifted interest to other vascular devices, particularly intravascular catheters, extracorporeal tubes, and blood circuits, where the challenges of prolonged anticoagulation and biofouling are critical. In this area, a study by [7] introduced a heparin network coating, which integrates adaptive antithrombosis and antibacterial activity through a cross-linked architecture that stabilizes heparin on the surface and maintains its functionality under flow. In human blood models and ex vivo testing of implanted catheters in rabbits, the authors reported a 60% reduction in thrombus adhesion and more than 97% bacterial inhibition, in addition to prolonged functional retention against shear and repeated use, underscoring its translational potential for long-stay catheters. This approach illustrates the shift toward multifunctional coatings, which seek to simultaneously address thrombosis and infection.

In addition, microgel-reinforced zwitterionic coatings have emerged as a benchmark passive solution: these coatings demonstrate low protein adsorption, high mechanical strength, and stability under continuous flow, even outperforming conventional hydrogels [19], [34]. Although they do not provide active anticoagulation like heparin, these surfaces offer a highly robust passive profile, making them a strategic complement to heparinized bases or structural polymers, providing a low coefficient of friction and resistance to degradation under physiological conditions [20], [35]. Overall, studies converge in that hybrid coatings that combine active anticoagulation with passive antifouling properties and a micro/nanostructured design represent the most promising way to overcome current limitations, consolidating a multifunctional approach that seeks to prolong the useful life of grafts and improve their biological integration in real clinical conditions.

However, significant challenges remain, such as durability under pulsatile flow, prevention of heparin shedding, and compatibility with flexible catheter geometry. Recent reviews of anti-fouling coatings for devices in contact with blood emphasize that standardization of hematic and tribological testing, including the definition of shear rates and physiological media, will be essential to compare technologies and accelerate clinical adoption [34]. These challenges show that, while experimental evidence is promising, the clinical translation of coatings on catheters and extracorporeal tubes still depends on long-term validation.

4.3. High-performance pumps, ventricular assist devices (VAD)

In mechanical valves, recent strategies have shifted from traditional inert layers to functional modifications that simultaneously seek hemocompatibility and hydrodynamic durability. A 2023 preclinical study evaluated a bioactive layer based on cross-linked (PEG) nanogels releasing ticagrelor and minocycline, demonstrating that the coating does not increase contact phase activation, while preventing protein adsorption, platelet adhesion, and thrombus formation without penalizing valve hydraulic performance. Methodologically, they combined standardized hydrodynamic assays, plasma hemocompatibility, and surface microscopy to verify coating integrity, durability, and antithrombotic effect functionality [36]. In addition, the 2024 reviews on surface modification in mechanical valves compare inorganic techniques such as diamond-like carbon (DLC) and TiN versus polymeric/bioinspired ones, highlighting that DLC provides a low coefficient of friction and wear resistance, which is key for hinges and contact surfaces, while NO-mimetic, anti-adhesive functionalized layers seek to limit platelet activation at the blood-material interface; the methodological consensus is to use hydrodynamic test benches, adhesion/abrasion assays, and blood panels such as thrombin and

370 platelets, as a complement to compare technologies under equivalent conditions [37]. In
371 the DLC family, recent work indicates that doping with Si, F, Ag, and tuning of mechan-
372 ical properties such as “soft DLC” can improve hemocompatibility and layer adhesion
373 without sacrificing low friction; Here, film characterization methodologies (XPS, AFM,
374 nanoindentation) are contrasted with hematologic assays and endothelial cell models to
375 correlate chemistry/tribology with biological response [38], [39].

376 In the context of ventricular assist devices (VADs), CBAS coating has been ob-
377 served to offer remarkable clinical durability, with reduced thrombus deposition over
378 prolonged periods of use [28], [40]. In parallel, 2022–2025 LVAD/ECMO reviews com-
379 pare the evolution of propellant, cannula, and oxygenator materials and surfaces: (i)
380 heparinized layers including CBAS seek to reduce thrombin activation and platelet ad-
381 hesion during prolonged support; (ii) NO-releasing platforms attempt to replicate endo-
382 thelial signals to inhibit platelet activation/inflammation; and (iii) optimized DLC low-
383 friction layers address hemolysis and wear in high-shear zones; overall, preclinical and
384 clinical results suggest mechanism-specific benefits, but no single strategy simultane-
385 ously resolves thrombosis, hemolysis, and biofouling, thus prompting hybrid integra-
386 tion and validation under comparable protocols [41]–[44]. Experiences in pumps, valves,
387 and VADs show that, although heparin-based strategies remain the gold standard, their
388 efficacy largely depends on the mechanical stability of the coating and its performance
389 under intense pulsatile flows. This raises the need to continue evaluating these surfaces
390 in contexts of prolonged use and high mechanical demand, where the durability of he-
391 mocompatibility is critical for clinical success.

392 5. Decision map

393 The selection of hemocompatible coatings must consider the interaction between
394 device type, flow regime, and mechanical function. Based on the findings in the previous
395 sections, a decision tree (Figure 1) can be established to guide the choice of surface or
396 coating type based on hydrodynamic requirements and clinical purpose.

397 At the top of the diagram is the first decision axis, corresponding to the type of
398 blood flow: pulsatile laminar flows typical of stents and vascular prostheses; continuous
399 extracorporeal flows, characteristic of catheters, tubes, and blood circuits; and intense
400 pulsatile or turbulent flows, present in mechanical valves, pumps, and VADs. Each of
401 these branches leads to a second decision level, which defines the coating's predominant
402 clinical objective: prevention of thrombosis, reduction of biofouling or associated infec-
403 tions, or prolonged mechanical and chemical durability under high shear conditions. At
404 a third level are the recommended coating strategies, derived directly from the analyzed
405 studies: for laminar flows, heparinized or hybrid heparin-collagen/TiO₂ surfaces such as
406 the CBAS system are prioritized, effective in inhibiting coagulation and preserving en-
407 dothelial function; for continuous extracorporeal flows, cross-linked heparin networks
408 or zwitterionic coatings reinforced with microgels are proposed, which offer mechanical
409 resistance and minimal protein adsorption; while in turbulent flow conditions and high
410 friction, layers of DLC doped with Si, F or Ag, or NO-mimetic surfaces are recom-
411 mended, capable of maintaining low friction, limiting hemolysis and preserving the in-
412 tegrity of the material in valves and VADs.

413 Finally, the base of the tree integrates the critical functional variables that determine
414 the effectiveness of any coating: its mechanical and chemical durability, the predominant

415 biological function (antithrombotic, antibacterial, or anti-friction), and its geometric com-
 416 patibility with the device surface, whether rigid or flexible. Overall, the decision tree
 417 reflects the technological progression described in the three previous sections, showing
 418 how the choice of the ideal coating depends on balancing flow conditions, clinical objec-
 419 tives, and the mechanical properties required to ensure sustained hemocompatibility for
 420 each type of device.

421
422 *Figure 1: Decision tree for hemocompatibility coatings.*

423 6. Gaps and test recommendations

424 Table 2 summarizes the most relevant findings from preclinical and clinical studies
 425 conducted between 2019 and 2025 on hemocompatible coatings applied to different fam-
 426 ilies of cardiovascular devices, ranging from stents and vascular prostheses to catheters,
 427 valves, and ventricular assist devices (VADs). This synthesis allows us to observe the
 428 progressive evolution of surface strategies and how each approach has responded to the
 429 specific challenges of each hemodynamic environment. In the case of stents and vascular
 430 prostheses, the studies by [21], [26], along with those by [20] and [31], consolidate the
 431 efficacy of CBAS-type heparin coating and heparin-collagen architectures deposited us-
 432 ing layer-by-layer methods, demonstrating a significant reduction in in-stent throm-
 433 bosis, improved endothelialization, and prolonged mechanical stability. However, the
 434 clinical efficacy of heparin continues to vary compared to drug-eluting stents, prompting
 435 the search for more stable hybrid compositions.

436 In extracorporeal catheters and tubes, advances focus on extending functional du-
 437 rability under continuous flow and preventing infections. The study by [7] introduced a
 438 cross-linked heparin network with adaptive antithrombotic and antibacterial properties,
 439 achieving a 60% reduction in thrombus adhesion and over 97% in bacterial inhibition,
 440 results that represent a qualitative leap toward the use of multifunctional coatings. In
 441 parallel, the work of [19] and [34] on zwitterionic coatings reinforced with microgels

demonstrated minimal protein adsorption and superior mechanical strength, making them promising alternatives for long-term extracorporeal systems where stability under constant shear is critical.

In the field of mechanical valves, the preclinical study by [36] tested a bioactive layer of ticagrelor- and minocycline-releasing PEG nanogels, verifying that the coating maintains blood functionality and hydraulic efficiency, while preventing platelet adhesion. Likewise, the investigations by [38] and [39] on DLC layers doped with silicon, fluorine, or silver highlighted the ability to tune the surface chemistry to reduce friction and improve adhesion, correlating these tribological properties with an improved endothelial response. Finally, the work of [40], [42], [44] on ventricular assist devices (VAD/ECMO) and pumps revealed that CBAS heparinized surfaces, together with nitric oxide releasing and hybrid DLC coatings, are able to decrease thrombus formation and attenuate hemolysis, although no single strategy comprehensively addresses the combined challenges of thrombosis, biofouling, and mechanical wear.

Reference	Device	Type of coating	Model	Principal results
[21], [26]	Stents	Heparin (CBAS)	Clinical trials	Partial reduction in in-stent thrombosis; efficacy varies depending on antiplatelet therapy.
[20], [31]	Vascular prostheses	Heparin–collagen (layer-by-layer)	In vivo / preclinic	Improved endothelialization without hyperplasia; acceptable mechanical stability.
[7]	Catheters	Crosslinked heparin network	Ex vivo (rabbit)	– 60% thrombotic adhesion; 97% bacterial inhibition; good flow stability.
[19], [34]	Extracorporeal tubes	Zwitterionic with microgels	In vitro / continuous flow	Minimal protein adsorption; superior mechanical strength to conventional hydrogels.
[36]	Mechanical valves	Nanogel (PEG + ticagrelor/minocycline)	Preclinical	Prevention of thrombi without loss of hydraulic performance.
[38]	Valves / moving components	Doped DLC (Si, F, Ag)	In vitro / cellular	Low friction and good adhesion; positive correlation between doping and hemocompatibility.
[40], [42], [44]	VAD / ECMO	CBAS, NO-mimetic, hybrid DLC	Clinical / multicenter	Reduction in thrombotic deposits; partial improvement in hemolysis; no single optimal strategy.

The Table 3 and Trial Recommendations identify the main scientific and experimental gaps that remain in the development and validation of hemocompatible coatings for cardiovascular devices. Although significant advances have been made in terms of bioactive functionality, antifouling, and durability, methodological and standardization limitations still exist that hinder objective comparisons between technologies and their translation into real-life clinical settings. In the case of stents and vascular prostheses,

available studies show a significant gap in direct comparisons between heparinized coatings such as CBAS and DES under equivalent conditions. This lack of methodological uniformity generates heterogeneous results and makes it difficult to establish clear clinical superiority. Therefore, the implementation of controlled in vivo trials is recommended, including standardized coronary flow models and follow-up periods of more than 12 months, simultaneously evaluating restenosis, thrombosis, and endothelial response under modern antiplatelet therapies.

In extracorporeal catheters and circuits, the main gap lies in the lack of standardized protocols for measuring durability and friction under prolonged continuous flows, which prevents reproducibility of results between laboratories. Despite the progress made with cross-linked heparin networks and zwitterionic coatings, flow benches with physiologically relevant shear rates, combined with tribological tests tailored to flexible geometries that simulate real-life operating conditions, are still required. Furthermore, mechanical valves present significant methodological fragmentation: tribological, hematic, and surface characterization studies are often addressed in isolation, making it impossible to correlate mechanical wear with platelet activation or thrombus formation. Therefore, it is proposed to integrate hydrodynamic, tribological, and hematic tests within a single protocol, incorporating characterization tools such as XPS, AFM, and nanoindentation along with biological assays for thrombin, platelets, and complement.

In the case of ventricular assist devices (VADs) and ECMO systems, the main limitation relates to the lack of long-term clinical validation for hybrid coatings, especially those combining heparin, nitric oxide (NO), and doped DLC layers. Preliminary results show benefits in reducing thrombus and hemolysis, but there are no multicenter studies that simultaneously evaluate the impact of these coatings on biofouling, degradation, and chemical durability under chronic support. In this context, prolonged and coordinated trials between institutions are recommended, allowing for robust comparative evidence under equivalent flow and mechanical loading conditions. Finally, across all categories, the lack of uniform metrics to quantify the so-called "hemocompatible durability" is notable; that is, the ability of a coating to maintain its antithrombotic, antifouling, and chemically stable properties over time. In response, the creation of an integrated hemocompatible index is proposed, which combines quantitative variables of protein adsorption, platelet activation, leaching and shear strength, reported under common experimental conditions.

Table 3: GAPS founded in the literature.

Category	Gap	Consequence	Test recommendation
Stents and vascular prostheses	Lack of direct comparisons between heparinized coatings and drug-eluting stents (DES) under equivalent conditions.	Heterogeneous results and difficult interpretation of clinical efficacy.	Design in vivo trials with controlled coronary flow models and follow-up ≥ 12 months, including quantification of restenosis and thrombosis under standard antiplatelet therapy.
Extracorporeal catheters and tubes	Lack of standardized protocols for measuring shear and adhesion under continuous flow.	It hinders reproducibility between laboratories and comparability of antifouling technologies.	Implement flow benches with defined blood parameters (viscosity, hematocrit, temperature), along with tribological tests adapted to the flexible material.
Mechanical valves	Fragmented evaluations between tribological and hematological properties.	Wear, friction and platelet activation are not correlated.	Integrate hydrodynamic, tribological, and hemocompatibility testing into a single standardized protocol; correlate

			XPS/AFM with thrombin and platelet assays.
VADs / ECMO	Lack of prolonged clinical validations (> 1 year) for hybrid coatings (heparin–NO–DLC).	Lack of comparative evidence versus conventional heparin in long-term support.	Multicenter studies combined analysis of hemolysis, thrombosis, and biofouling under chronic support conditions.
General / trans-vascular	Absence of common metrics for “hemocompatible durability”.	Inability to compare results between device types.	Define an integrated hemocompatible index (adsorption + activation + leaching + shear) reported under uniform conditions.

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500 **References**

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